

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B048
 Date: 03 Sep 2004
 Take Off 06:07:01 12:57:26
 Landing: 10:58:57 16:40:10
 Flight Time 4h51m56 3h42m44

Trials Instructions: ADRIEX – pollution from Western and Eastern Europe
Operating Area: N Italy to the Black Sea and back

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	Dropsondes	Steve Devereau	FAAM
7	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	CVI	Paul James	FAAM
9	VACC	Stuart Heath	FAAM
10	Bottle filling	Ken Dewey	FAAM
11	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
12	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
13	Filters	Paola Formenti	CNRS/University of Paris 12
14	AMS	Jonny Crosier	UMIST
15	TDL / WAS / PAN / Tubes	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
16	Nephelometer / PSAP	Jolene Cook	Reading University
17	Mission Scientist 2	Simon Osborne	Met Office
18	Mission Scientist 3	Elisabeth Ostrom	Met Office
19	Ground crew	Martin Darling	Avalon Aero
20	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B048
 Date: 03/09/04
 Project: ADRIEX
 Location: Black Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
045000		UBBRs	-.18 kft	024	Covers OFF
053830		INU	-.17 kft	024	To NAVIATE
060701		T/O	2.1 kft	240	Treviso
081748	082424	Run 1	25.0 kft	096	
082215		Sonde	25.0 kft	097	Launch 01
082437	082706	Profile 1	25.0 - 22.7 kft	097	1000fpm , Interrupt
082913	083629	Profile 1	22.7 - 14.1 kft	300	
083400		TERRA	16.2 kft	301	Overpass
083835	084506	Profile 1	14.1 - 7.7 kft	139	
084500		ATSR			Overpass
084657	084953	Profile 1	7.7 - 4.6 kft	328	
085100	085445	Profile 1	4.6 - 0.16 kft	066	
085658	085920	Profile 1	1.6 - 0.82 kft		
090004	090124	Profile 1	0.82 - 0.05 kft		
090505	090630	Orbit 1	0.50 up & down		45deg,LH start 150
090800	090928	Orbit 2	0.50 up & down		start 330
091056	091337	Orbit 3	0.50 up & down		start 150
091337	091506	Orbit 4	0.50 up & down		start 330
092246	092416	Orbit 5	0.35 - 0.21 kft	312	38deg,LH start 330
092548	092715	Orbit 6	0.48 - 0.28 kft	146	start
092830	092959	Orbit 7	0.25 - 0.28 kft	324	start 330deg
093119	093253	Orbit 8	0.35 - 0.29 kft	136	start 150deg
093938	094439	Run 1.1	1000ft	171	
094607	095107	Run 1.2	1000ft	355	
095129	095240	Profile 2	-.01 - 0.66 kft	000	
095209		PSAP 1	0.37 kft	359	Change Filter
095734	100635	Run 2	1.0 kft	179	
100733	101017	Profile 3	1.0 - 3.0 kft		
100920		PSAP	3.2 kft	325	Pump OFF, cloud
101324		PSAP	3.2 kft	008	Pump ON
101117	102111	Run 3	3.5 kft	008	
102213	102432	Profile 4	3.2 - 5.4 kft	103	1000fpm
102611	102801	Profile 4	5.5 - 7.0 kft	286	
102904	103652	Run 4	7.0 kft	192	
103826	104324	Profile 5	7.0 - 12.0 kft	345	1000fpm
104507		Sonde	12.0 kft	245	Launch 02
104530	104911	Run 5	12.0 - 9.3 kft	244	
105857		Land	0.05 kft	184	Constanta
					Refuel
110941		INU Align	0.04 kft	129	44'20.83N, 028'28.91E
124333		INU NAV	0.05 kft	129	
125726		T/O	1.1 kft	002	Constanta
125726	130401	Profile 6	0.0 - 5.0 kft	147	
130546	131131	Run 6	5.0 kft	106	
131131	131409	Profile 7	5.0 - 3.3 kft	102	
131516	131722	Orbit 9	3.3 kft	004	35deg,RH,start060
131841	132006	Orbit 10	3.3 - 3.4 kft	189	start 190deg
132130	132258	Orbit 11	3.5 - 3.2 kft	266	start 270deg
132414	132541	Orbit 12	3.3 kft	046	start 060deg

132736	132855	Run 7	3.2 kft	064
132855	133108	Profile 8	3.2 - 4.9 kft	059 1000fpm
133302	134049	Run 8	5.0 kft	253 Into Sun
134203	134333	Profile 9	5.0 - 6.0 kft	009 1000fpm Down Sun
134340	135108	Run 9	6.0 kft	067
135218	140033	Profile 10	6.0 - 15.0 kft	199 1000fpm
140142		Sonde	15.0 kft	283 Launch 03
140235	140915	Run 10	15.0 kft	287
140420		Sonde	15.0 kft	288 Launch 04
153451		Neph Time	26.0 kft	287 50s slow
153517		PSAP Time	26.0 kft	287 10s fast
164010		Land	-.16 kft	069 Treviso
165059		GPS Posn	-.16 kft	024 45'39.18N, 012'12.13E

B048 Track 03-SEP-04

1 INCH=20 NAUTICAL MILES

WOMK 4 B

WEST SECTOR

FAAM Sortie Brief

ADRIEX: pollution from Western and Eastern European Pollution.

Flight No: B048

Date: 3rd September 2004

Trial objectives:

To determine the physical, chemical and radiative properties of aerosols from east European pollution sources.

Location:

The Black Sea.

Weather:

Anticyclonic conditions; cloudless skies; advection of pollution over sea areas.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Treviso airport at 0600 GMT [0mins]
2. High speed transit out towards Constanta at FL250 [140mins]
3. Carry out a broken profile descent from FL250 to 50ft off the coast of the Black Sea [170mins]
4. Perform a set of 4 orbits banked at ~45deg at 500ft [180mins]
5. Carry out a 10min holding pattern [190mins]
6. Perform a set of 4 orbits banked at ~45deg at 500ft [200mins]
7. Carry out a stacked profile ascent to FL150, interrupting to perform 10 min straight and level runs at 5 levels orientated into- and down- Sun; the levels will be called by the aircraft scientist [270mins]
8. Carry out a broken profile descent from FL150 to 50ft [290mins]
9. Transit and land at Constanta [305mins]
10. Refuel
11. Take-off Constanta 1300 GMT [0mins]
12. Transit out at low level to the operating region over the Black Sea [10mins]
13. Perform a set of 4 orbits banked at ~45deg at 500ft [20mins]
14. Carry out a 10min holding pattern [30mins]
15. Perform a set of 4 orbits banked at ~45deg at 500ft [40mins]
16. Carry out a stacked profile ascent from 50ft to FL150, interrupting to perform 10 min straight and level runs at 5 levels orientated into- and down- Sun; the levels will be called by the aircraft scientist [100mins]
17. Perform a box pattern at FL150 consisting of 5 min legs with outside turns; the legs to be orientated into-, across-, down- and across- Sun [130mins]
18. High speed transit back to Treviso at FL250 [270mins]
19. Land Treviso airport.

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B048

Date: 3rd September 2004

Sortie Objectives: ADRIEX flight to investigate pollution over the Black Sea.

Operating area: Transit, followed by operations over ocean areas off the coast of Romania within the Bucharest FIR. Transit back.

Weather: In the operating area there was a clear slot with no cloud at all. Further off the coast there was a gradual increase in cumulus humulus, with more significant cloud fractions on occasion during the flight. A layer of pollution extended from close to the surface to approximately 2,000ft, followed by the tenuous cloud layer and another separate layer of pollution from approximately 5,000ft-10,000ft. No Ci was encountered during the operational science part of the flight.

Flight Patterns:

Subsequent to take off from Treviso at ~06:05Z, a long transit was performed to Constanta, Romania. During this transit SWS was operated, and was operated as a sun-photometer for a portion of the flight as the run was exactly into-sun (fortuitously) Over the Black Sea, a run was commenced and a sonde was dropped from FL250. It might be possible to diagnose the direct radiative forcing from the lower BBRs as there was little (if any) in the way of cloud present for much of R1. A profile descent was made from FL250 to 50ft, although this profile was interrupted several times for ATC, and operating area restrictions. A series of 8 orbits were then performed at ~500ft using the Haywood manoeuvre to prevent gyro jamming. A SLR at 100ft was then performed in two legs; into- sun and down- sun. There was a little Cu around and though SWS should work OK, probably the upper BBRs will not work as a method for determining the aerosol optical depth. Subsequently a short profile ascent to 1000ft was performed where an into-sun SLR was performed. Good run for the SWS and BBRs. A short profile ascent to 3500ft was performed, followed by a SLR at 3500ft. At this level we were above all of the Cu, but below the majority of the upper pollution layer. A run was then performed within the main pollution layer at 7,000ft, before a run above the pollution layer at FL120 was performed. A sonde was dropped and during this run the lower BBRs could probably be used to determine the direct radiative effect. The aircraft then recovered to Constanta for re-fuel.

Having refuelled, take-off was at ~12:58Z. A SLR was performed for a short time at FL50, followed by a set of 45degree banked orbits at 3,500ft, which was above the low level pollution layer, but below the upper pollution layer. This should enable the difference in the upper and lower pollution layers to be determined from measurements of the sky radiance with the SWS. The solar zenith angle was around 55degrees so the SWS instrument was run without neutral density filters. Two into and down sun SLRS were then performed at FL50 and FL60 within the upper aerosol layer. A profile ascent was then made to FL150, and two sondes were dropped (the first did not produce winds). During the run at FL150, there was no cloud below for a significant period of time, and the lower clear BBR showed approximately 110Wm^{-2} suggesting a significant direct radiative effect. Subsequently a long transit was performed back to Treviso though little science was performed except for SWS work.

Problems:

Ci intrusions.

PSAP recorded onto Paola's laptop.

Nephelometer recorded onto a FAAM laptop.

The problem with the nephelometer and PSAP had been diagnosed following the previous flight to a problem with bit 10 of the neph and PSAP DLU. This may prove tricky to account for.

PCASP missing 3 smallest channels.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Temo 08:34
Aqua 10:16
AATSR 08:45

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Date **3 sept 2004**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
~06:07					T/O Treviso
					Very hazy, no cloud.
					Visibility ~ 5-10km.
					Top of haze ~ 5000 ft.
					ETA Constanta 08:18.
08:08	R1	FL250			Sat overpasses MODIS T 08:34
					MODIS A 10:16
					AATSR 08:45
					SWS got a couple of measurements @ FL250 into sun (by luck).
					Also requested step angle scanning e.g. 10° off sun, 20° off sun, 30° etc.
08:16					Crossing Black Sea coast.
08:17:48	R1 st	FL250			Cloud to the RHS & ahead. // might be able to get DRG?
					Cu starting off coast
08:22:15	Drop #1	FL250			Sonde #1.
08:24:24	End R1				Cu below, very scattered << 1/8.
08:24:37	PI st	FL250 ↓			End Run.
08:27:06	Int PI	FL227			Turn back towards land.
08:29:13	Recom R1	FL227 ↓			O ₃ , CO + SO ₂ scanning structure, <u>Towards land</u> away from
08:36:29	Int PI	FL140			Haze below
08:38:34	Recom PI	FL140 ↓			Top of layer ~ 10,500 ft.
					<u>Away from land</u>

Top 10,000

Aircraft Scientist's Log

T 08:34
A 10:16
AA 08:45

100ft ✓
~~200ft~~
1000ft
3000ft
7000ft

Flight No **B.049**

Date **3 Sept 2004**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	
					Continuing away from land Profile	
08:45:13	Int PI	FL800			Towards land	
08:47:03	Recom PI	FL50 ↓			←	
08:49:53	Int PI	FL50			Redirection to cloud free-ish area	
08:51:00	Recom PI	FL50 ↓	050M		Cloud tops at 2500ft Cloud bottom at 2000ft. Rate change to 500ft/minute under cloud.	
08:54:45	Int PI	1600ft			Very hazy.	
08:56:58	Recom PI				Some oil rigs.	
	Int PI	820ft			Hazy.	
	Recom A		268T			
09:01:24	End PI	50ft				
					Set-up for orbits.	
					Orbits, free from cloud	No cloud
	St O1	500ft			40° RWD orbit.	Good
09:06:30	End O1	5			manouver	
	St O2	540ft			40° RWD orbit	
09:09:23	End O2	50			Free from all cloud.	
09:10:56	St O3	500ft				
09:12:24	End O3					
09:13:37	St O4	540ft	330M		Excellent!!!	
	End O4				Rockets being fired in a closeby range.	

12,000 Not into sun / down sun

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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Date **3 Sept 2004**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09:22					Repositioning + holding pattern for 2nd set of albits.
09:22:46	St 05	500ft			Variations about 150ft. Good!
09:24:16	End 05				
09:25:48	St 06	500ft			
09:27:15	End 06				
09:28:30	St 07	500ft			
09:29:59	End 07				
09:31:13	St 08	500ft			
09:32:53 09:31	End 08				
					Repositioning for SHRs into & down-sun. Trying to find best cloud-free
09:39:38	St R2.1	100ft	172T		Sea state 3/4 12kts. <u>Into-sun</u> A few scattered cu ← 1/8.
09:44:39					SWS will find areas through.
09:46:07	St R2.2	100ft	356T		— " — <u>Down-sun</u>
					BBRs might be worth a look, but probably not.
09:51:29	End R1.2				Profile ascent
- " -	St P2	100ft ↑			
09:52:40	End P2	1000ft			Into-sun run.
10:57:40	St R2	1000ft			Into-sun run.
					BBRs could be used in first part until ~ 10:00:00

06Z
T10

or maybe further.
~~VERY~~ GOOD news esp we have BRE + AOD

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...048**

 Date **3 Sept**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:04:40	-				No Ci in region so far at all.
					<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 50%; padding: 5px; margin-right: 10px;"> Into-sun Run </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> 10,500 Pollution top pollution 2000-2500 cloud pollution surface </div> </div>
10:06:35	End R2				Turn followed by profile ascent.
10:07:33	St P3	1000ft [↑]	280M		
10:10:17	End P3 / St R3	3,500ft			Cu below, ^{upper} BBRs can be used here for good analysis. 4/8 Cu below. Down-sun
10:21:11	End R3	3,500ft			Lower pollution at end of run
10:22:13	St P4	3,500ft [↑]			1000ft/min.
					Climb into main pollution @ 4000ft
10:24:32	Int P4	5,500ft			Interrupt Profile.
	Restart P4	5,500ft [↑]			No cloud above, lots of haze.
10:26:11	End P4	7,000ft			
10:29:04	St R4	FL070			Into-sun run. — Good for BBR (appear)
10:36:52	End R4	FL070			
10:38:26	St P5	FL70 [↑]			Start profile ascent.
10:43:24	End P5	FL128			End profile.
10:45:07	D#2				Very little cloud below
10:45:30	St R#5	FL120			§ Lower BBRs could be

used, probably from a little before + further.
We have DRE + AOD.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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 Date **3 Sept 2004**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:49:11	End R5				
					Top of aerosol ~ 10,000ft.
					No time for profile descent.
					Very hazy throughout descent.
					Lots of agriculture around Constanta.
					Burning agriculture on RTHs on approach to airport.
					Landing 1020 kg LTHs 1100 kg RTHs.
					== Refuel Constanta, Romania
~ 12:58:30					Take off Constanta.
					Quite a few small biomass fires.
					Mainly agricultural land
13:01:51	St P6	3,600ft↑			Ragged 1000ft/min
13:04:01	End P6	5,000ft			profile ascent to FL50
13:05:46	St R6	FL50↗			Very hazy at this level
					A few very scattered Cu ahead and below. No upper cloud.
13:11:31	End R6 / St FL50↓				Profile descent.
13:14:09	End P7	3,500ft			
13:16:49	St O9	3,500ft			45° RHD banked orbits.
13:17:22	End O9				

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.048**.....

 Date **3 Sept 2004**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					First orbit v. good.
					No Ci above.
13:18:41	St 010	3,500ft	190		Below haze layer (but above MBL haze). In clear slot. 45°
13:20:06	End 010				
13:21:30	St 011	3,500ft			45° RWD orbit
13:22:58	End 011				
13:24:14	St 012	3,500ft			45° RWD orbit.
13:25:41	End Orbit 12				
13:27:36	St R7				Start run.
13:28:55	End R7 St P8	3,500ft↑			End run. 1000ft/minute profile ascent.
13:31:08	End P8	5,000ft			
13:33:02	St R8	5,000ft			Extremely good → no cloud above or below for all this run, except the very end.
13:40:49	End R8	5,000ft		no snapshot 0.86	SWS working as photometer despite SZA. (rough 1000 ft as bring interfering)
13:42:03	St P9	5,000ft↑		SZA 58°	
13:43:33	End P9	6,000ft		no 0.86	
13:44:07	St R9	6,000ft			Excellent run in thick haze
13:51:08	End R9	6,000ft		SZA 62°	SWS working as photometer despite SZA.
13:52:18	St P10	6,000ft↑			Profile ascent.
					Top of haze diffuse at 8,500ft → 10,000ft.
					A strange chemistry & neph signal at the very top of the aerosol layer observed

30 miles ~ 3min Cluins

2000
12000
- 2000
10000 kg

Aircraft Scientist's Log

< 7000ft > 18000ft

Flight No **B...048**.....

Date**3/09/04**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	P(cont)				FL40 → very clear above with thick haze below, a few Cu too
14:00:33	end P10				← 1/8
14:01:42	D#3				
14:02:35	Start R10	FL150			Can use data before this, but cloudy.
14:03:45					Cloud below has gone.
14:04:20	D#4	FL150.			Good for BBR DRE here lower clear BBR = 110 W m ⁻² and steady!! No Ci above, no Cu below.....
14:09:15	End R10/C10	FL150 ↑			Climb to FL270, not a profile, but could use the data.
15.04.00		FL260	294		do cloud around aircraft, very hazy over mountain scattered sheets of stcu ahead and to right
150630					CuNi on left far away ~ 100 miles layer of Ci ahead with Alst/stcu below
150940		FL260	293		red neph above green! sampling artifact? hazy above low cloud and above ci
151400					Very moist between stcu "moist bubbles"
15.22					6/8 stcu with Ci in front very hazy between stcu
15.32			298		less stcu much more haze below long line of ci ahead crossing flight path at right angle

flight path at right angle
↓

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B048

Date: 3/9/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
08:17:48			U/S								Star Run 1 @ FL250
08:18:00	2										
08:20:00	2										
08:22:00	2										
08:24:26											End of Run 1
08:24:38	2										Start Profile 1 From FL250
08:25:40	1										FL240
08:26:42	2										FL230
08:29:55	2										FL220
08:30:58	5										FL210
08:31:37	5										FL200
08:32:20	5										FL190
08:33:13	6										FL180
08:33:58	1										FL170
08:34:50	2										FL160
08:35:45	3										FL150
08:36:35	5										FL140
08:39:25	5										FL130
08:40:30	5										FL120
08:41:43	130			2							FL110
08:42:40	400			5							FL100
08:43:42	300			5							FL090
08:44:45	400			5							FL080
08:47:30	500			5							FL070
08:48:38	700			5							FL060
08:49:40	500			5							FL050
08:51:55	500			5							FL040
08:52:55	140			5							FL030
08:53:45	900			10							FL020
08:58:12	1000			10							1000'
09:00:30	800			10							500'
09:01:26	600			10							End of Profile 1

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B048

Date: 3/9/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:05:05											Start Orbits
09:15:06											End of Orbits (4)
09:22:48	HEATER	OFF									Start Orbits
09:32:56											End of Orbits (8)
09:39:40											Start Run 1.1 @ 100'
09:40:00	700			10							
09:42:00	680			10							
09:44:00	740			10							
09:44:42											End of Run 1.1
09:46:10											Start Run 1.2 @ 100'
09:47:00	680			10							
09:49:00	640			10							
09:51:10											End of Run 1.2
09:51:25	600			10							Start Profile 2 from 100'
09:52:43	550			10							End of Profile 2 @ 1000'
09:57:40											Start Run 2 @ 1000'
09:58:00	650			10							
10:00:00	650			10							
10:02:00	700			10							
10:04:00	730			10							
10:06:00	650			10							
10:06:38											End of Run 2
10:07:34	680			10							Start Profile 3 from 1000'
10:08:50	660			10							2000'
10:09:55	200			10							3000'
10:10:17	400			10							End of Profile 3 @ 3500'
10:11:20											Start Run 3 @ 3500'
10:12:00	300			10							
10:14:00	340			10							
10:16:00	320			10							
10:18:00	350			10							
10:20:00	170			10							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B048

Date: 3/9/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:21:14											End of Run 3
10:22:16											Start Profile 4 from 3500'
10:23:11	330			2							FL040
10:44:10	300			2							FL050
10:26:50	370			2							FL060
10:28:00	300			2							End of Profile 4FL070
10:29:04											Start Run 4 @ FL070
10:30:00	340			2							
10:32:00	320			2							
10:34:00	310			2							
10:36:00	300			2							
10:36:55											End of Run 4
10:38:30	315			2							Start Profile 5 from FL070
10:39:28	300			2							FL080
10:40:25	260			2							FL090
10:41:20	210			2							FL100
10:42:20	20										FL110
10:43:25	4										End of Profile 5 @ FL120
10:45:33											Start Run 5 @ FL120
10:46:00	1										
10:48:00											
10:50:12											End of Run
13:57:56	HEATER	ON									Start Profile 6 from FL120
13:04:01											End of Profile 6 @ FL050
13:05:46											Start Run 6 @ FL050
13:06:00	430			2							
13:08:00	410			2							
13:10:00	480			2							
13:11:30											End of Run Start P7 from FL050
13:13:01	550			2							FL040
13:14:11	410			2							End of Profile 7 @ 3800'
13:16:00											Start Orbits

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B048

Date: 3/9/04

Operator: MAP

Page 4 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
13:25:41											End of Orbits (12)
13:12:36											Start Run 7 @ 3500'
13:28:00	100			5							
13:29:09											End of Run 7 Start P8 from 3500'
13:30:15	310			5							4000'
13:31:12	310			5							End of Profile 8 @ 5000'
13:33:05											Start Run 8 @ 5000'
13:34:00	380			5							
13:36:00	440			5							
13:38:00	440			5							
13:40:00	480			5							
13:40:52											End of Run 8
13:42:06	370			5							Start Profile 9 from FL050
13:43:36	360			5							End of Profile 9 @ FL060
13:44:11											Start Run 9 @ FL060
13:45:00	480			2							
13:47:00	510			5							
13:49:00	480			5							
13:51:09											End of Run 9
13:52:23	440			5							Start Profile 10 from FL060
13:53:27	350			5							FL070
13:54:28	300			5							FL080
13:55:26	310			5							FL090
13:56:25	160			5							FL100
13:57:12	25			5							FL110
13:58:06	5			5							FL120
13:58:55	5										FL130
13:59:44	5										FL140
14:00:46											End of Profile 10 @ FL150
14:02:40											Start Run 10 @ FL150
14:03:00	5										
14:05:00	5										

SWS/SHIMS PRE-FLIGHT LOG		Date	3/9/07	Flight	B 048
Operator(s)			Campaign	ADREX	
Departure			Arrival		

Physical system setup

Module Number	Connection(e.g.SWS nir, SHIMS upper)
0	SWS nir
27581	SWS vis

System functionality check **After system stabilizes**

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0 sec	at time	0600Z
Freezer temp	-6°C			

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 048	Date	3/9/04	Operator(s)	A. WILSON	log page	1	of	4
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times	Remarks East-west flight. Black Sea.				
				Vis	NIR				

061100			0°			Dark current view.			
065800						TRANSIT TO Black Sea.			
065830			54°F	Auto		almost flying into sun. Having a look			
071600			54°F	Auto	Solar	Azimuth 115.8°. INS heading 99.4°.			
						SWS signals probably Sun reflection off aircraft fuselage.			
072400	TRANSIT	250	50°F	Auto		Solar azimuth 117.8°. INS heading 120°			
						Almost directly into Sun. Will perform a series of 10° fore → Aft scans. FILTERS <u>NOT</u> fitted.			
072715	TRANSIT	250	40°F	Auto					
072940		250	30°F						
073130		250	20°F	Auto		Changing course now. Heading to			
073630	transit	250	10°F	Auto		Constanta. Zenith 121°. INS heading 103°.			
073840		250	0°	Auto		Zenith 123.3. INS heading 105.9°.			
074155		250	10°A	Auto		Zenith 124. INS heading 106.9°			
074425		250	20°A	Auto		- - - 125.6 - - - 106.8°			
074630	TRANSIT	250	30°A	Auto		- - - 125.6 - - - 107.1			
074840			40°A	Auto		- - - 127.1 - - - 107.6			
075120	TRANSIT	250	50°A	Auto		127.9 107.75			
075450			60°A	Auto		129.5 103.66			
080000	Transit	250	0°	Auto		131.2 104.2°			
						end of transit.			
081748	R1	250	0°	Auto		Start R1			
081934						Video start			
082215	Sonde 1	250	0°	Auto		Dropsonde 1			
082430	R1	250	0°	Auto		end R1			
082437	P1	250	0°	Auto		Start P1 FL250 → 50ft			
082706	P1	22700	0°	Auto		int P1			
082913	P1	22700	0°	Auto		restart P1			
083638	P1	14000	0°	Auto		int P1			
083834	P1	FL140	0°	Auto		restart P1			
084512	P1	FL076	0°	Auto		int P1			
084703	P1	FL076	0°	Auto		restart P1			
084953	P1	FL046	0°	Auto		interrupt P1			
085100	P1	FL046	0°	Auto		restart P1			
085445	P1	1600ft	0°	Auto		int P1			
085658	P1	1600ft	0°	Auto		restart P1			
	P1		0°	Auto		interrupt			
090000	P1		0°	Auto		restart P1			
090154	P1	50ft	0°	Auto		end P1			

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B068** Date **3/9/04** Operator(s) **A. Wilson** log page **2** of **4**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

090340		400ft	6°F	10	10	for orbits.
090505	orb.1	400ft	6°F	10	10	40° right wing down.
090630	"- 1	400ft	6°F	10	10	end
090800	"- 2	400ft	6°F	10	10	start orbit 2
090928	"- 2	400ft	6°F	10	10	end orbit 2
091056	"- 3	400ft	6°F	10	10	start 3
091224	"- 3	400ft	6°F	10	10	end 3
091337	"- 4	400ft	6°F	10	10	start 4
091506	"- 4	400ft	6°F	10	10	end 4
092100						ND 30 FILTERS FITTED TO NIR & VIS *
092246	orb.5	400ft	6°F	10	30	38° orbit right wing down
092416	" 5	400ft	6°F	10	30	end orbit 5
092548	"- 6	400ft	6°F	10	30	start 6
092715	"- 6	400ft	6°F	10	30	end 6
092830	"- 7	400ft	6°F	10	30	start 7
092959	"- 7	400ft	6°F	10	30	end orbit 7
093119	"- 8	400ft	6°F	10	30	start 8
093253	"- 8	400ft	6°F	10	30	end orbit
093500			0°	Auto		
093938	R1.1	100ft	44°F	Auto		into sun run - Zenith 37.2 pitch 5.6 Numerous small fragments of bkn Cu above.
094439	R1.1	100ft	44°F	Auto		end R1.1
094607	R1.2	100ft	31°A	10	30	Down sun run Zenith 37 pitch 5.4
095107	R1.2	100ft	31°A	10	30	end R1.2. Manual integration chosen as more stable
095129	P2	100ft	31°A	10	30	start P2
095240	P2	100ft	32°A	10	30	end P2
095740	R2	100ft	44°F	10	30	into sun. Zenith 37.4 Pitch 5.74
100635	R2	100ft	44°F	10	30	end R2
100733	P3	100ft	0°	10	30	start P3 → 3000ft
101017	P3	3500ft	0°			end P3
101117	R2.1	3500ft	31°A	10	30	down sun. Zenith 36.8° Pitch 5.1 IR Max ~ 31°A. Vis Max ~ 31°A
102115	R2.1	3500ft	31°A	10	30	end R2.1
102213	P4	3500ft	0°	Auto		start P4 → FL070
1024	P4	5500ft	0°	Auto		int P4
102611	P4	5500ft	0°	Auto		restart P4 → FL070
102801	P4	FL070	0°	Auto		end P4
102904	R4	FL070	~43.5°F	15	30	into sun. Zenith 37.8 Pitch 5.5
103652	R4	FL070	~43.5°F	15	30	end R4
103826	P5	FL070	0°	Auto		P5 → FL120
104324	P5	FL120	0°	Auto		END P5

Filters
Fitted

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B048** Date **3/9/04** Operator(s) **A. Wilson** log page **3** of **4**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

↑
FILTERS
FITTED
↓
*

104510	FL120	FL120				
104530	R5	120	0°	Auto		
110000						LAND @ CONSTANTIA.
111000						Video Stop
111103						DARK CURRENT VIEW
111000						FILTERS REMOVED. *
124845						DARK CURRENT VIEW
	SORTIE		PART 2			
125000						VIDEO START
125120			90°A			DATA START
12573420	P6					TAKE OFF FROM CONSTANTIA.
130401	R6/c	050	0°	Auto		
130546	R6	050	0°	Auto		
131131	R6	050	0	Auto		
131138	P7	050	0	Auto		
131412	P7	3500ft	0°	Auto		
131615	orbit 9	3500ft	6°F	30	75	start orbit 9
	--- 9	3500ft	6°F	10	50	end 9. Vis integration changed to prevent saturation of signal
13	--- 10	3500ft	6°F	10	50	Good. No signal integration.
132026	10	3500ft	6°F	10	50	Solar glaze just off RHS of Video screen
132130	--- 11	3500ft	6°F	10	50	
132301	--- 11	3500ft	6°F	10	50	
132414	--- 12	3500ft	6°F	10	100	increased NIR int to boost signal.
132541	--- 12	3500ft	6°F	10	100	end orbits.
						FILTERS FITTED ND3 Vis & NIR *
133330	R8	5000ft	50°F	Auto		INDO SUN RUN zenith 58.5 Pitch 6.7
133442	R8	5000ft	40°F	Auto		WING obscures view. scanning instead
133645	R8	5000ft	30°F	Auto		
133804	R8	050	20°F	Auto		
133926	R8	050	10°F	Auto		
134020	R8	050	0°	Auto		
134050	R8	050	10°A	Auto		
134055	R8	050	0°			
1342	P	050	0°	Auto		P → FL060
134332	P	060	0°	Auto		
	R9	060	53.5°A	15	30	Down Sun Run.
134940	R9	060	55°A	15	30	zenith 61.8° Pitch 6.82°
135108	R9	060	55°A	15	30	end of R9
135218	P10	060	0°	Auto		P10 → FL150

*
Filters
Fitted
↓

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: B048	DATE: 03/09/2004	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	PAGE: 1 of 2
LOCATION: The Black Sea		PROJECT: ADRIEX – pollution from Western and Eastern European Pollution.	

GAS CYLINDER PRESSURES	Argon/CO2	N2	CO	HORACE
PRE FLIGHT	psi / bar	psi / bar	psi / bar	-- n/a --
POST FLIGHT	psi / bar	psi / bar	psi / bar	-- n/a --

TIME (GMT)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	CO SENSITIVITY (Hz/ppbV)	CO BACKGROUND (ppb)	CO BCKGRD.CNT.B (Hz)	CO CONC. (ppb V)	O3 (ppb)	NO (ppb)	NO2 (ppb)	NOx (ppb)	SO2 (ppb)			
02/09/04			87.99	59.34	5221.08									
12:15:30	Remarks: Last calibration from previous flight/ground test for comparison with today.													
03/09/04	ground	-	83.85	60.56	5077.57	427.573	1	94.6	99.2	193.9	8.43			
05:35:09	Flow Lamp:	33.91	Press Monocr	0.61	Press Cell:	7.13	Press Cal Gas	2.52	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	26.15	PMT °C	26.10
Remarks: First cal of day Air sample pipe (ASP) closed. CO cal max values : 497 - 529														
05:43:09	ground	-	82.72	62.18	5143.57	425.411	0	47.0	-2.2	44.8	5.38			
Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 518 - 524														
06:03:17	ground	taxiing	88.90	61.24	5444.14	115.715	1	22.0	13.2	35.2	4.91			
	Flow Lamp:	33.90	Press Monocr	0.61	Press Cell:	7.13	Press Cal Gas	2.51	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 562 – 595														
06:25:40	FL150		84.23	61.81	5206.32	66.212					-			
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: ASP open. CO cal max values : 493 – 497 – poor, cal repeated below														
06:30:35	FL250		84.30	61.42	5177.87	64.484	55	-0.24	0.37	0.14	7.62			
Remarks: CO cal max values : 523 – 527 - better														
07:10:45	FL250	transit	87.58	59.36	5198.97	61.126	61	-0.17	0.35	0.18	7.19			
	Flow Lamp:	33.91	Press Monocr	0.46	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.42	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	25.51	PMT °C	25.45
Remarks: CO cal max values : 545 – 548														
07:25:03	FL250		87.96	59.10	5198.76	67.988	82	0.19	0.22	0.40	6.99			
	Flow Lamp:	33.91	Press Monocr	0.45	Press Cell:	7.13	Press Cal Gas	2.42	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values : 526 – 531														
07:31:03	FL250		88.22	59.02	5206.50	62.458	-	-	-	-	-			
Remarks: 525 - 528														
08:07:59	FI250	P	88.33	58.48	5165.78	82.643	65	-0.04	0.24	0.20	7.48			
	Flow Lamp:	33.96	Press Monocr	0.45	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.41	Lamp °C	-	Monocr °C	-	PMT °C	-
Remarks: CO cal max values : 525 - 527														
08:26:01	FL250 – FL235	R1->P1	88.81	58.17	5166.47	87.128	60	0.10	0.34	0.44	6.57			
	Flow Lamp:	33.91	Press Monocr	0.47	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.39	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values : 527 - 531														
09:06:37	200'?	Into O1	91.83	57.91	5317.63	127.516	48	-0.00	0.75	0.75	3.98			
	Flow Lamp:	33.85	Press Monocr	0.60	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.51	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values : 547 – 544 Note: O1 started 09:04:														
09:21:09	200' ?	-	92.45	57.36	5303.14	135.637	53	0.05	0.91	0.96	3.94			
	Flow Lamp:	33.91	Press Monocr	0.60	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.52	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values : 526 - 518														
10:14:00	FL030	-	91.17	57.11	5206.45	117.508	54	-0.00	0.31	0.35	4.03			
	Flow Lamp:	33.91	Press Monocr	0.60	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.52	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values : 516 - 518														
10:31:40	FL070	-	90.17	57.53	5187.78	108.154	59	-0.13	0.57	0.49	4.45			
Remarks: CO cal max values : 518 - 524														
10:40:36	FL120		89.96	57.14	5140.77	83.703	62	-0.02	0.09	0.09	4.66			
	Flow Lamp:	33.90	Press Monocr	0.56	Press Cell:	7.16	Press Cal Gas	2.48	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values : 521 - 527														
12:01:12	ground	Constanta	89.70	57.85	5188.67	135.061								
Remarks: ASP closed.														
12:47:27	ground	Constanta	88.04	58.48	5149.21	140.456	41	-0.11	0.10	-0.01	7.17			
Remarks: ASP closed. TECO Nox cal run at same time as CO cal.														

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: B048	DATE: 03/09/2004	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	PAGE: 2 of 2
LOCATION: The Black Sea		PROJECT: ADRIEX – pollution from Western and Eastern European Pollution.	

TIME (GMT)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	CO SENSITIVITY (Hz/ppbV)	CO BACKGROUND (ppb)	CO BCKGRD.CNT.B (Hz)	CO CONC. (ppb V)	O3 (ppb)	NO (ppb)	NO2 (ppb)	NOx (ppb)	SO2 (ppb)
12:58:19	ground	taxiing	91.60	57.99	5311.62	128.33	53	0.03	0.01	0.04	8.63
	Flow Lamp:	33.21	Press Monocr	0.60	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.50	Lamp °C	Monocr °C	PMT °C
Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 546 - 566											
13:07:30	FL050	Into R6	87.35	58.87	5142.23	108.739	58	-0.01	0.55	0.54	4.57
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C	Monocr °C	PMT °C
Remarks: ASP open. CO cal max values :498 – 503 NOx zero ended part way through this calibration.											
13:17:57	FL035	Into O9	86.85	58.94	5119.01	113.436	54	-0.07	0.54	0.46	4.49
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C	Monocr °C	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 520 - 524											
13:35:33	FL050	Into R	86.65	59.10	5120.63	122.210	53	-0.19	0.72	0.33	3.96
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C	Monocr °C	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 520 – 526 Calibration is bad message during first section – allowed instrument to continue to end of cal											
13:47:45	FL060	Into R	86.22	59.26	5109.15	118.368	59	0.01	0.68	0.69	4.24
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C	Monocr °C	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 520 - 525											
14:04:12	FL150		86.41	58.89	5088.59	71.628	62	0.00	0.15	0.16	5.10
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C	Monocr °C	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 525 - 529											
15:00:56	FL260	-	89.99	56.06	5045.13	61.376	57	-0.08	0.32	0.23	-
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C	Monocr °C	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 548 - 545											
::											
Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values :											

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...048...

Date ...3.9.04.....

Page ...1... of ...3...

Video Tapes		GPS	INU	DRS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
(V8)		Lat	45°39.18N	45°39.16N
No.		Long	12°12.06E	12°12.06E
Ends		Time	05:59:14	055847
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC		Status	✓	NAV
				HORACE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
				SATCOM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

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GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
060701	TAKE OFF	FROM	TREVISO					
								Transit to Black Sea area @ FL250, DFC recording
		P1		EVM				
083635	140	Interrupt	P1					Horace filter problems.
083834	FL140	Recomm	P1	2				
084512	FL77	Int	P1					
084703	FL77	Recomm.	P1					
084953	FL46	Int	P1	3				
085100	FL46	Recom	P1					
085339	3000'	close	PSAP	Pump.				
085407	2000'	change	rod	to 500fpm,				psap pump on.
085445	1600'	Interrupt	P1					
085658	1600'	Recom.	P1	6.				
085920	1600' 1200'	Int	P1	7				
090004	820'	Recom	P1	8				
090124	50'	END	P1	1				
090505	500'	START	ORBIT 1,	45° LH,				start 150° and climbing
090630	500'	END	01					
090800	500'	START	02	start 330°			090928	END 02
090928								
091056	500'	START	03,	hdg 150°			091224	END 03
091337	500'	START	04,	hdg 330°			091506	END 04
				150°				
				(No Flight on Sun Adriatic + Po Valley)				
095740	1000'	START	RUN 2	Into Sun				
100635	1000'	END	RUN 2					

 150
 3000
 1000
 7000
 120

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...048....

Date ...3.9.04.....

Page 2 of 3...

Video Tapes		GPS	INU		
(V8)		Lat	44'20.83N	44'20.83N	DRS <input type="checkbox"/>
No. #2		Long	28'28.91E	028 28.91E	HORACE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Ends 1320.		Time	12:26:32	12:25:49	SATCOM <input type="checkbox"/>
FFC / RFC / (DFC) / (UFC)		Status	✓	ALIGN	

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GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
100733	1000 1000	START	PROF	PROFILE	3.	100907		
101017	3000'	END	P3					
100920	PSAP	Pump	off	- into	cloud.			
101324	PSAP	Pump	ON					
101117	22	3500'	START	RUN 3				
			END	RUN 3				FLTD ETA 1100Z
105857	LAND	AT	CONSTANTA		(4h55)			
		Refuel						
125726	TAKE OFF	FROM	CONSTANTA					
131138								
131138	END	RUN 6	/	START P7				
131412	END	P7						
		START	ORBIT 9,	45°		start 060°		
132301	END	011						
		START	012					
134055	END	RUN 8.						
134208	START	P9						
134340	END	P9	/	START	RUN 9.			
	50.	seconds	slow	-	Neph time	(ie Neph behind a/c)		
	10.	seconds	faster	than	a/c -	PSAP		
140920.	END	RUN 10	FLISU					
					31 50.	160 2140		1705
					11431	+10s.		
		Neph, Ozone						

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B.048**.....

Date **3.9.04**.....

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU			<u>Probes</u>		
GPS		✓	FFSSP		✓
Satcom C		✓	PCASP		✓
Satcom H			2D-P		
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	X	
De-Iced Temp		✓	Cloudscope	✓	
Non De-Iced		✓	SID 1		✓
Heimann		✓	SID 2	X	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI	X	
G. Eastern		✓	HVPS	X	
J. Williams		✓	<u>Racks:</u>		
Nevzorov	X		INC	X	
TWC	X		CCN / <u>CNC</u> only	X	✓
FWVS			CVI		✓
<u>Radiometers</u>					
Upper Clear			<u>Aerosol</u>		
“ Red	✓	✓	PSAP		✓
“ Silicon	✓	X	Nephelometer		✓
“ JO1D	✓		AMS		✓
Lower Clear					
“ Red	✓	✓			
“ Silicon	✓				
“ JO1D	✓	X			
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	X				
MARSS	X				
DEIMOS	X				
ARIES					
SWS / SHIM	✓	✓			
<u>Chemistry</u>					
Ozone	✓				
ECGC	X				
NOX	✓				
CO	✓		<u>Others:</u>		
ORAC	X				
PAN	X				
PERCA	X				
WAS	✓				

Terra
0834

ATSR
0845

AQUA,
1016

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. 8048

Instruments

1. Aerack DLU - On DRS plot, Ch 177 NBTS show Bit 10 is always zero. This is also the case for Ch 180 NBBS (which is on a separate DLU card). (~~bit 15 low on Neph channels too.~~)
2. Horacc plotting flt sum problem again at 0839. Came back for a while then problems again after selecting Trk Plot. Later problems went away when sws closed 3 windows. Seems ~~be~~ fairly random though as to what cures the problem.
3. Neph - data logged on FAAM1 laptop (as well as DLU).

Aircraft

• kations:

B048 03-Sep-04 08:27:55 000 (04:12:35) 44.15 30.0

Event mark

<input type="radio"/> 175.NPRS	2291	26867	<input type="radio"/> 185.PLIN	535	21015	195.FILTER 1 FLOW
<input checked="" type="radio"/> 176.NTMP	108	45164	<input type="radio"/> 187.PTRN	2817	47873	196.FILTER 1 PRESSURE
<input type="radio"/> 177.NBTS	2071	18455	<input type="radio"/> 188.PFLO	145	32913	197.FILTER 2 FLOW
<input type="radio"/> 180.NBBS	2085	18469	<input type="radio"/> 198.F2PR	3879	15167	198.FILTER 2 PRESSURE